

AZORES DEESEA RESEARCH

**MAPGES 2025 CRUISE REPORT: EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA
BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON-BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO**

INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS DO MAR - OKEANOS, UNIVERSIDADE DOS AÇORES, HORTA, PORTUGAL

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1 SUMMARY OF THE MAPGES 2025 CRUISE ON-BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO

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Date: 30 September 2025

1.1 MAIN OBJECTIVES

MapGES 2025 continues our longstanding commitment to map deep-sea biodiversity and identifying Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) in the Azores with the Azor drift-cam imagery system. Our 2025 expedition aimed to enhance the data collected in previous surveys by conducting new video transects along seamounts over a widespread area in the Azores archipelago, namely the new area at the southern limit of the EEZ (Pico Sul), the seamounts and ridges east of Terceira Island and a variety of sites along the Mid-Atlantic ridge and adjacent areas. This fieldwork focused mostly on under-sampled areas and deeper strata. Our ultimate goal is to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the deep-sea fauna dwelling on the slopes, banks, and seamounts in these areas. Like previous MapGES cruises, our objectives included: (i) mapping benthic communities in previously unexplored seamounts, ridges, and island slopes; (ii) identifying new areas that meet the FAO definition of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems; and (iii) determining the distribution patterns of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the Azores. The results of this cruise added to the previous contributions to identify the environmental drivers that determine the spatial distribution of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the Azores. It also provides valuable information in the context of Good Environmental Status (GES), Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and new insights on how to sustainably manage deep-sea ecosystems.

1.2 METHODOLOGY

We conducted several underwater video transects along the seafloor using the Azor drift-cam, a cost-effective drifting camera system developed by IMAR and Okeanos at the University of the Azores. This system is capable of recording high-quality underwater video images and it was deployed from the RV Arquipélago. This year, the operation capabilities of the Azor drift-cam were expanded to ~1500 m depth. In each sampling area, we performed a representative number of dives using the video system, ranging from approximately 1200 m to the shallowest point of each structure. The objective was to capture underwater images that would effectively characterize the biodiversity across the entire bathymetric gradient and various substrate types. The video transects were strategically planned based on the most accurate bathymetric data available, allowing the camera system to drift from deeper to shallower regions. This methodology was designed to ensure optimal image quality by maximizing light incidence and minimizing attenuation in the water column, a challenge typically encountered during descending transects. Each transect with the Azor drift-cam was planned for approximately 60 to 120 minutes on the seafloor, with the system drifting over benthic habitats at an average

speed of 0.5 to 1 knot. Under favourable conditions, each working day facilitated 5 to 6 dives, corresponding to approximately 5 kilometres of seafloor explored daily.

Vessel:

RV Arquipélago

Dates:

Leg 1: 16th to 24th August

Leg 2: 27th August to 5th September

Scientific team:

Leg 1: João Balsa (Chief scientist), Inês Bruno, Manuela Ramos, Marc Pladevall Vilavendrell

Leg 2: Luís Rodrigues (Chief scientist), Gabriela Cardoso, Guilherme Gonçalves, Inês Bruno

1.3 STATISTICS

Overall, we performed 55 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1234 m depth, covering 75.8 km of the seafloor and producing more than 74 hours of video footage of the seabed (Table 1).

Leg 1: We performed 23 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to > 1200 m depth, covering 17.7 km of seafloor and producing around 25 hours of video footage, 1.7 TB of disc space.

Leg 2: performed 32 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1230 m depth, covering 26.6 km of the seafloor and producing 49 hours of video footage, 2.3 TB of disc space.

Figure 1. Scientific teams that participated in the different legs of the MapGES 2025 Cruises on the RV Arquipélago.

1.4 CRUISE SUMMARY

The MapGES 2025 cruise aboard RV Arquipélago consisted of 2 legs and aimed at exploring and revisiting banks, ridges, and seamounts on the south limit of the EEZ of the Azores, south of São Miguel in Mar da Prata, East of Terceira Island and in the Mid-Atlantic ridge. We spent only 16 full workdays at sea, compared to the 34 initially planned, which forced us to reprioritize and exclude several objectives. Exploration of seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic ridge and additional areas around Pico and São Miguel had to be cancelled, reducing the cruise's scope. Further delays arose from technical and mechanical issues beyond the team's control.

A total of 55 successful dives were conducted out of 56 planned, covering 16 sampling areas. During **Leg 1**, from the 16th to 24th of August, we performed 23 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam. These first deployments surveyed the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the slopes of the geomorphological structures at the southern limit of the EEZ (Pico Sul), in the southern area of Mar da Prata and in structures located east of Terceira Island (Heitor Álvares, Alcatraz and Dom João de Castro). This first leg aimed to complete surveys in areas long on our priority list, while also exploring two previously unsampled sites: Pico Sul, located about 230 nm south of Faial Island, and Heitor Álvares. During **Leg 2**, from 27th August to 5th September, a total of 32 successful dives were conducted with the Azor drift-cam. This Leg aimed at exploring seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic ridge and adjacent areas, some visited for the first time, others revisited to complement earlier surveys.

A major objective of this year's cruise was to assess potential faunal differences between an isolated, deep seamount (Pico Sul) and other sites already studied. Fauna at Pico Sul proved sparse and of low density. By contrast, the eastern peaks of the Alcatraz structure hosted particularly interesting assemblages, with several individuals of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*, the rarely recorded glass sponge *Asconema cf. setubalense*, and multiple specimens of the sponge *Hertwigia falcifera*. Similar to recent observations from the northern Mar da Prata sectors, assemblages of a seemingly shallow morphotype of *Candidella imbricata* were recorded, possibly indicating a wide distribution of this species across the entire geomorphological complex. The shallow dives conducted in Dom João de Castro showed extensive and dense coral gardens essentially composed by *Viminella flagellum*, *Dentomuricea aff. meteor* and *Callogorgia verticillata*. We also explored and revisited several Azorean seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, documenting unexpected biodiversity and novel records for us. At Ferradura E, we recorded one of the densest aggregations of *Hertwigia falcifera* recorded in the region and vast ridges dominated by *Narella* spp. with frequent colonies of black corals *Leiopathes expansa*. At the newly named Fantas seamount, we observed a possible first Azorean record of a Mid-Atlantic skate *Rajella cf. kukujevi*. At Menez Gwen, long drift-cam transects revealed recent pillow lavas colonized by large *Leiopathes expansa* and *Placogorgia* sp. Picoto seamount hosted one of the largest aggregations of *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia* sp. recorded in the region, while Alfa seamount hosted impressive *Paragorgia johnsoni* "forests" and diverse associated fauna.

Table 1. Areas surveyed during each of the legs of MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, with information on number of dives, total distance of seafloor covered, and number of hours recording video footage on the seafloor.

Leg	Dates	Areas explored	Dives (n)	Dist. (km)	Bottom time (hh:mm)
1	16/08/2025 – 24/08/2025	Pico Sul, Mar da Prata S, Heitor Alvares, Alcatraz, Dom João de Castro	23	17.7	25:27
2	28/08/2025 – 04/08/2025	Ferradura E, Beta, Beta W, Buchanan N, A10 (Fantas), A13, Menez Gwen, Picoto, Alfa Profundo, Alfa, Alfa E	32	27.0	49:11
Total			55	44.7	74:38

Figure 2. Location of the 55 video stations carried out with the Azor drift-cam during the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Figure 3. Some highlights of the footage recorded during the Legs 1 and 2 of MapGES 2025 on board the RV Arquipélago. (a) Spot of what it seems to be a Pyrossomatid under a basaltic boulder in the isolated seamount Pico Sul; (b) Aggregation of the shallow morphotype of the primnoid coral *Candidella imbricata* at Mar da Prata S; (c) Assemblage of the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*; (d) Basaltic boulder with the uncommonly spotted glass sponge *Asconema cf. setubalense*; (e) Isolated and robust colony of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*; (f) Large hexactinellid sponge *Hertwigia falcifera*; (g) Basalt overhangs sheltering *Leiopathes expansa* and large plate-shaped demosponges; (h) Slopes colonized by the bubblegum coral *Paragorgia johnsoni*; (i) Impressive colony of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* attached to an outcrop and hosting the decapod *Sternostylus formosus*; (j) Massive hexactinellid sponge *Chonelasma sp.*; (l) Potential first record in the Azores of the Mid-Atlantic skate *Rajella cf. kukujevi*; (m) Community composed by the look alike coral species *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia sp.*

1.5 MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

1. During the MapGES 2025 survey conducted aboard the RV Arquipélago, **55 stations were completed** using the Azor drift-cam. The performed stations spanned depths ranging **from 230 to 1234 m**, encompassing a broad spectrum of marine strata. The survey covered approximately **45 km** of the seafloor and generated **more than 74 hours** of video footage for analysis. These numbers represent a big achievement considering that we successfully operated, once again, the Azor drift-cam with several improvements, including an umbilical cable of 1500m, the underwater positioning system (USBL), the external power feeding of the GoPro camera and the addition of a second spotlight.
2. We visited **one of the most isolated and offshore seamounts** of the Azores EEZ, Pico Sul. This geomorphological structure is at a total distance of around 230 nm from Faial Island. The transit took more than 27h to reach this area and is among the furthest areas ever explored with the Azor drift-cam.
3. **The deepest and longest dives with the Azor drift-cam** were carried out during this year's survey: the deepest at Pico Sul, largely exceeding 1200 m, the longest in distance at Menez Gwen (~2.6 km), and the longest in terms of duration at Beta, lasting more than 3 hours.
4. At the newly explored A10 area, our cameras captured a very pale, ghost-like ray that lingered calmly in front of the system. This sighting may represent the first record of the Mid-Atlantic skate (*Rajella* cf. *kukujevi*) in the Azores. Inspired by this unusual encounter, the **site was renamed "Fantas" seamount**, short for *Fantasma* ("ghost" in Portuguese). The A13 seamount is yet to be renamed.
5. The deeper strata, including the intermediate and lower slopes of the visited seamounts, **harboured lush benthic communities, visibly thriving on the seafloor**. The richness, abundance, and environmental conditions of many of these assemblages were unexpected, especially as some areas surveyed in the past revealed substantially poorer megabenthic communities. These observations demonstrate how quickly one's perception of a seamount's ecological value can change with a few complementary dives and additional seafloor coverage. They also highlight the importance of systematic and repeated exploration to capture the full extent of habitat diversity, ensuring that future spatial planning and conservation measures are grounded in comprehensive and representative knowledge.
6. This year's survey revealed **contrasting patterns of benthic diversity, from sparse communities at Pico Sul to notably rich assemblages in other areas**. At this isolated seamount, benthic megafaunal assemblages appear limited, with most species occurring solitarily. Such patterns may offer preliminary clues to the structure of communities on deep, isolated seamounts.
7. **The black coral *Leiopathes expansa* and the glass sponge *Hertwigia falcifera* were frequently spotted on the multiple outcrops and overhangs found**. During the exploration of Ferradura E area, the deeper sectors revealed **unique and localized megabenthic communities** usually composed of a large variety of species. We recorded what we think could be **one of the densest aggregations of the large yellow hexactinellid *Hertwigia falcifera***. The increment in the observations of these species can also be influenced by the deeper sectors explored this year.
8. Thriving benthic fauna was observed on the deep eastern summits of Alcatraz, **including a localized patch of the rarely seen glass sponge *Asconema* cf. *setubalense* on a basaltic boulder. This was possibly the first record of this species with the Azor drift-cam**.
9. Dense assemblages of a **shallow morphotype of *Candidella imbricata*** point to a broad ecological footprint of this primnoid coral within Mar da Prata complex. This interpretation is supported by the remarkable aggregations documented during last year's survey in Mar da Prata N.

10. Shallow dives at Dom João de Castro revealed **extensive coral gardens dominated by *Viminella flagellum*, *Dentomuricea aff. meteor*, and *Callogorgia verticillata***. Nevertheless, the pervasive presence of lost fishing lines highlights the ongoing human impact on these fragile communities.
11. In Ferradura E seamount, our cameras documented a **vast and dense aggregation of the primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*** at around 850 m depth, extending along almost an entire ridge. While *Narella*-dominated communities are common across many Azorean seamounts, the diversity recorded along this ridge surpassed that observed at most comparable depths.
12. The **Menez Gwen area** revealed as an enigmatic area. We could not have picked a better spot to perform the **longest dive to date with the Azor drift-cam**. To start with, the substrate on particular sectors was impressive, with apparently **geologically recent pillows** with very little to no sediment deposition. In addition to this, scattered along these recent hardgrounds were impressive **large-sized colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* and of the genus *Placogorgia***, with occasional lace corals *Lophellia pertusa* also composing this interesting benthic community.
13. The deep, wide and long ridge that extends for 15 nm in a south-to-north orientation in **Picoto seamount revealed rich megabenthic communities**. One of the surveyed sectors revealed a surprisingly diverse megabenthic assemblage, contrasting with the rather modest impression we had while navigating the system in real time. An **extensive aggregation of the corals *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia sp.* was observed, likely among the largest and densest yet recorded in the Azores**.
14. At Alfa seamount we documented particularly remarkable communities, especially on the shallowest and intermediate slopes surveyed. These sectors hosted a **“forest” of massive *Paragorgia johnsoni* (bubble-gum coral) colonies**, exhibiting both morphotypes, but mostly white. These are certainly among the **largest examples of this species observed with our camera system to date**.

1.6 STATIONS SURVEYED DURING MAPGES 2025 CRUISE ONBOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO

During MapGES 2025 cruise on board the RV Arquipélago we successfully completed a total of 55 dives out of the 56 stations attempted in 16 different sampling areas (Table 2).

Table 2. Compilation of the stations surveyed during MapGES 2025 cruise on board the RV Arquipélago.

Station	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End Position		Depth		
			Time_start	Time_end	Lat_start	Long_start	Lat_end	Long_end	Start	End	Dist
St001	Pico Sul	17/08/2025	08:24:46	11:03:33	34.8385	-27.5025	34.8224	-27.4953	1131	907	1900
St002	Pico Sul	17/08/2025	12:34:25	13:52:15	34.8203	-27.4658	34.8265	-27.4662	1266	1160	690
St003	Pico Sul	17/08/2025	16:02:02	17:02:14	34.8509	-27.5264	34.8552	-27.5210	1194	1103	680
St004	Mar da Prata S	18/08/2025	12:21:58	13:23:20	37.1222	-25.6354	37.1170	-25.6423	989	765	840
St005	Mar da Prata S	18/08/2025	14:17:07	15:05:58	37.1368	-25.6412	37.1322	-25.6487	787	730	830
St006	Mar da Prata S	18/08/2025	16:32:04	17:08:51	37.2060	-25.6684	37.2032	-25.6722	814	313	450
St007	Heitor Alvares	19/08/2025	08:31:27	10:24:25	38.6279	-25.9176	38.6236	-25.9089	1026	878	890
St008	Heitor Alvares	19/08/2025	11:33:20	12:57:34	38.6105	-25.9074	38.6147	-25.9009	811	586	730
St009	Heitor Alvares	19/08/2025	14:15:14	15:26:20	38.6128	-25.8854	38.6097	-25.8818	745	620	460
St010	Heitor Alvares	19/08/2025	16:37:08	17:05:05	38.6088	-25.8687	38.6080	-25.8684	793	795	90
St011	Heitor Alvares	19/08/2025	18:43:40	19:33:42	38.5907	-25.8601	38.5949	-25.8573	1148	1095	520
St012	Heitor Alvares	20/08/2025	08:54:24	09:47:54	38.5544	-26.1101	38.5579	-26.1071	692	674	460
St013	Heitor Alvares	20/08/2025	11:42:59	13:03:50	38.5465	-26.1029	38.5506	-26.0975	776	693	650
St014	Alcatraz	20/08/2025	16:33:26	18:02:54	38.1939	-26.2033	38.1865	-26.2089	969	712	950
St015	Alcatraz	21/08/2025	08:27:25	09:39:36	38.1813	-26.1162	38.1944	-26.1189	1010	1004	1470
St016	Alcatraz	21/08/2025	11:12:08	12:55:35	38.1581	-26.0541	38.1716	-26.0455	1076	981	1670

Station	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End Position		Depth		
			Time_start	Time_end	Lat_start	Long_start	Lat_end	Long_end	Start	End	Dist
St017	Alcatraz	21/08/2025	15:03:07	16:01:20	38.2221	-26.2197	38.2284	-26.2172	607	444	730
St018	Dom João de Castro	23/08/2025	08:30:05	09:18:46	38.2629	-26.6012	38.2616	-26.6098	883	844	760
St019	Dom João de Castro	23/08/2025	10:31:51	11:46:26	38.2460	-26.5465	38.2494	-26.5548	1029	905	810
St020	Dom João de Castro	23/08/2025	12:33:30	13:53:31	38.2423	-26.5676	38.2459	-26.5778	650	627	970
St021	Dom João de Castro	23/08/2025	14:50:11	15:24:05	38.1984	-26.5851	38.2013	-26.5900	604	484	530
St022	Dom João de Castro	23/08/2025	16:19:27	16:40:50	38.2189	-26.5695	38.2206	-26.5734	366	405	380
St023	Dom João de Castro	23/08/2025	18:10:27	18:31:45	38.2079	-26.6098	38.2091	-26.6131	355	245	310
St024	Ferradura E	28/08/2025	08:31:26	10:18:29	38.3272	-30.0816	38.3214	-30.0863	673	550	760
St025	Ferradura E	28/08/2025	11:12:00	12:48:59	38.3356	-30.0550	38.3343	-30.0579	1031	1025	290
St026	Ferradura E	28/08/2025	14:11:08	14:49:14	38.2806	-30.0671	38.2810	-30.0634	1034	1075	320
St027	Ferradura E	28/08/2025	16:11:32	19:02:40	38.2598	-30.1223	38.2550	-30.1145	865	836	860
St028	Beta	29/08/2025	08:35:14	09:51:55	38.2460	-30.9793	38.2416	-30.9726	962	923	760
St029	Beta	29/08/2025	10:59:39	12:24:40	38.2706	-30.9640	38.2629	-30.9598	888	753	930
St030	Beta	29/08/2025	13:38:30	14:37:54	38.3027	-31.0106	38.3018	-31.0062	781	808	390
St031	Beta	29/08/2025	15:55:20	19:07:48	38.2997	-31.0757	38.3049	-31.0481	1030	648	2470
St032	Beta W	30/08/2025	08:32:42	10:36:44	38.3330	-31.2374	38.3264	-31.2360	1107	937	740
St033	Beta W	30/08/2025	12:13:15	14:00:35	38.3222	-31.2555	38.3169	-31.2587	989	961	650
St034	Beta W	30/08/2025	15:19:53	16:25:30	38.3183	-31.2732	38.3163	-31.2755	1054	959	290
St035	Beta W	30/08/2025	17:27:00	19:28:05	38.3054	-31.2928	38.3036	-31.2963	838	786	360
St036	Buchanan N	31/08/2025	08:29:21	10:31:46	38.3276	-31.6247	38.3303	-31.6342	1088	946	880
St037	Buchanan N	31/08/2025	11:41:02	13:31:30	38.3569	-31.6112	38.3594	-31.6227	1054	859	1040
St038	Buchanan N	31/08/2025	14:56:02	16:01:35	38.4126	-31.5504	38.4181	-31.5604	1205	944	1060
St039	Buchanan N	31/08/2025	17:32:43	19:37:10	38.4782	-31.5196	38.4795	-31.5314	1065	905	1030
St040	Fantas	01/09/2025	08:39:50	10:46:46	37.7683	-32.1064	37.7616	-32.0944	936	995	1290
St041	Fantas	01/09/2025	12:23:47	14:53:05	37.8302	-32.1343	37.8182	-32.1254	1107	1019	1540
St042	A13	01/09/2025	17:35:42	17:37:43	37.8616	-31.8109	37.8617	-31.8100	980	973	70
St043	A13	02/09/2025	08:20:19	09:43:51	37.8457	-31.8124	37.8499	-31.7921	949	1040	1840
St044	Menez Gwen	02/09/2025	12:02:01	14:44:36	37.8425	-31.5417	37.8503	-31.5126	844	1022	2690
St045*	Menez Gwen	02/09/2025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
St046	Menez Gwen	02/09/2025	17:45:10	19:30:05	37.8211	-31.5546	37.8229	-31.5416	868	884	1150
St047	Picoto	03/09/2025	08:21:25	10:01:55	37.8702	-31.1891	37.8636	-31.1924	872	675	780
St048	Picoto	03/09/2025	11:14:58	12:21:02	37.8318	-31.1628	37.8327	-31.1661	1171	1139	300
St049	Picoto	03/09/2025	13:33:38	14:38:25	37.8035	-31.1929	37.7991	-31.1884	1082	1038	620
St050	Picoto	03/09/2025	16:18:12	17:16:25	37.7692	-31.1903	37.7653	-31.1884	962	942	460
St051	Alfa Profundo	03/09/2025	18:39:45	19:51:47	37.7588	-31.0928	37.7527	-31.0953	970	928	710
St052	Alfa	04/09/2025	08:29:08	09:28:29	37.7804	-30.8879	37.7809	-30.8919	978	1038	350
St053	Alfa	04/09/2025	10:39:02	11:48:20	37.7679	-30.8808	37.7765	-30.8756	676	747	1050
St054	Alfa	04/09/2025	12:56:53	14:28:20	37.7732	-30.7864	37.7762	-30.7782	994	958	790
St055	Alfa E	04/09/2025	16:14:15	17:11:14	37.7359	-30.6913	37.7368	-30.6868	735	733	400
St056	Alfa E	04/09/2025	18:10:49	18:26:10	37.7379	-30.6556	37.7380	-30.6534	773	726	190

*Dive not valid

2 MAPGES 2025 RV ARQUIPÉLAGO: EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES: LEG 1 –PICO SUL SEAMOUNT AND SEAMOUNTS EAST OF TERCEIRA ISLAND.

2.1 SUMMARY OF THE LEG1 OF MAPGES 2025 ARQUIPÉLAGO CRUISE

Objective: to conduct a rapid appraisal of the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the slopes of the geomorphological structures on the south limit of the EEZ of the Azores, named Pico Sul, in the southern sector of Mar da Prata and in structures east of Terceira Island (Heitor Álvares, Alcatraz and Dom João de Castro), on board of the Research Vessel Arquipélago. These dives aim to contribute to the overall goal of better understanding the composition and diversity of deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species and assess their environmental status.

Statistics: We performed 23 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to >1200 m depth, covering 17.7 km of the seafloor and producing 25 hours of video footage, 1.7 TB of disc space.

Vessel: RV Arquipélago

Dates: 16th - 24th August 2025

Scientific team: João Balsa (Chief scientist), Inês Bruno, Manuela Ramos and Marc Pladevall Vilavendrell

Figure 4. Scientific team of RV Arquipélago that participated in the Leg 1 of MapGES 2025.

2.2 HIGHLIGHTS

- 1- During Leg 1 of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, we were able to perform **23 valid dives** with the Azor drift-cam, covering a wide range of depth strata (**245 - > 1200 m depth**). We explored about **18 km** of the seafloor and produced **25:27** hours of video footage, adding up to about **1.7 TB** of storage space.
- 2- **We successfully sampled two new geomorphological units, Pico Sul and Heitor Álvares.** Other previously visited areas required more thorough coverage, either in depth range or spatial extent. With the Azor drift-cam's recent improvements in lightning, video durability, and operational depth range, we revisited these sites to obtain higher-quality data.

- 3- We explored **depths greater than 1200 m** - a first for the Azor drift-cam - which, once more, proves the **camera system's effectiveness and capabilities** in covering large bathymetric gradients, with all its components successfully handling the high pressures of the most demanding environments.
- 4- We visited **one of the most isolated and offshore seamounts** of the Azores EEZ, Pico Sul. This geomorphological structure is at a total distance of **around 230 nm from Faial Island**. After more than 27 hours of transit, **we reached one of the most remote areas ever explored with the Azor drift-cam**.
- 5- **No Azor drift-cam structures were lost during the survey**. On at least two occasions, the system became entangled in lost fishing lines, with one incident requiring over an hour to fully disentangle the structure. The Azor drift-cam, however, is purposely designed to minimize such risks, once again demonstrating both the reliability of its design and the skill of the operating and scientific team.
- 6- This year's survey revealed **contrasting patterns of benthic diversity, from sparse communities at Pico Sul to notably rich assemblages in other areas**. At this isolated seamount, benthic megafaunal assemblages appear limited, with most species occurring solitarily. Such patterns may offer preliminary clues to the structure of communities on deep, isolated seamounts.
- 7- **The black coral *Leiopathes expansa* and the glass sponge *Hertwigia falcifera* were frequently spotted on the multiple outcrops and overhangs found**. The increment in the observations of these species can also be influenced by the deeper sectors explored this year.
- 8- Thriving benthic fauna was observed on the deep eastern summits of Alcatraz, **including a localized patch of the rarely seen glass sponge *Asconema cf. setubalense* on a basaltic boulder. This was possibly the first record of this species with the Azor drift-cam**.
- 9- Dense assemblages of a potential **shallow morphotype of *Candidella imbricata*** point to a broad ecological footprint of this primnoid coral within the geomorphological framework of the Mar da Prata complex. This interpretation is supported by the remarkable aggregations documented during last year's survey in Mar da Prata N.
- 10- Shallow dives at Dom João de Castro revealed **extensive coral gardens dominated by *Viminella flagellum*, *Dentomuricea aff. meteor*, and *Callogorgia verticillata***. Nevertheless, the pervasive presence of lost fishing lines highlights the ongoing human impact on these fragile communities.

Figure 5. Location of the 23 video transects (yellow lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 1 of MapGES 2025 on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Figure 6. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 1 of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago showing examples of megabenthic fauna and communities recorded during the cruise: **(a)** Spot of what it seems to be a Pyrossomatid under a basaltic boulder in the isolated seamount of Pico Sul; **(b)** Evidence of the sparse and scarce benthic megafauna found in Pico Sul, here with the observation of a boulder hosting a few encrusting sponges, the black coral *Antipathes dichotoma* and a deep water plexaurid; **(c)** Aggregation of the shallow morphotype of the primnoid coral *Candidella imbricata* at Mar da Prata S; **(d)** Overhangs hosting an interesting benthic community composed of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*, bamboo corals *Acanella arbuscula*, lamellate sponges and whip-like plexaurids; **(e)** Basaltic boulder with the uncommonly spotted glass sponge *Asconema cf. setubalense*; **(f)** Isolated and robust colony of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*; **(g)** An exemplar of the massive and deep sponge *Hertwigia falcifera*; **(h)** Consolidated substrate with a strong presence of massive demosponges; **(i)** Spot of a very large individual of the hexactinellid sponge *Chonelasma* sp.; **(j)** Coral gardens with *Callogorgia verticillata*, *Dentomuricea aff. meteor* and *Viminella flagellum* are present in Dom João de Castro despite the numerous lost fishing lines; **(k)** Another example of a coral aggregation in Dom João de Castro this time with *Callogorgia verticillata* and the yellow morphotype of *Viminella flagellum*; **(l)** Assemblage of the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*.

2.3 CRUISE DIARY OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO LEG 1

16 August 2025

The start of the 2025 mission aboard RV Arquipélago was delayed due to mechanical and electric problems with the vessel. We departed Horta harbour at 01:00, towards Pico Sul, an isolated seamount about 230 nautical miles from Faial Island, at the limit of the Azores EEZ, arriving 27 hours later. The long transit provided time to prepare for the first day of work, check and repair equipment, adjust the recently adapted USBL pole, and strengthen bonds with the ship's crew. After a calm and pleasant crossing, we arrived at our destination at 04:00 with everything ready to begin operations.

17 August 2025

We arrived at the first work area for Leg 1 around 03:30 and remained on site drifting. We anticipated a challenging day primarily due to the morphology of the Pico Sul area, its limited bathymetric resolution, and the fact that a large portion of this seamount lies deeper than 1200 meters. A total of 3 dives (St001-003) were performed between 907 and 1266 m depth (based on bathymetric data rather than depth sensor readings).

Sea conditions were favourable, and the day began with a southeast drift. Before the first deployment, we identified an issue with the analog-to-digital video converter in the live-view system, which was promptly replaced. The first dive proceeded smoothly, benefiting from the natural drift and the captain's precise handling of the vessel. During the second dive, we believe we may have surpassed the deepest dive ever attempted with the Azor drift-cam. However, upon deployment, the drift developed in the opposite direction of what we expected. The fact that the drift camera reached depths below 1200 m demonstrates its remarkable capacity to survey even greater depths safely and efficiently. The third dive faced similar challenges as the previous, with the drift again pulling the system away from the intended direction. To counter this, we repositioned the deployment point further south of the mount, making two adjustments before achieving a relatively stable drift to the northeast.

Overall, the seabed was characterized by sedimentary rock layered with soft sediments accumulated throughout all the transects. The faunal assemblages on Pico Sul were very similar across all dives, likely due to the very limited bathymetric range explored. The area predominantly features a sedimentary depositional environment with cemented substrates and bottoms composed of sand and bio detritus (including coral rubble). Sparse observations of corals such as *Hemicorallium tricolor* and *Acanella arbuscula* were made on the sedimentary rock, along with some rare sponges like *Polymastia* sp. Less frequently, other corals such as *Muriceides paucituberculata*, *Antipathes dichotoma*, *Parantipathes hirondelle*, and possibly *Anthothela grandiflora* were encountered. Hexactinellid sponges, including *Pheronema carpenteri* and *Regadrella phoenix*, were common at shallower depths. The most frequent mobile invertebrates included *Cidaris cidaris* and some *Chaceon affinis*. Additionally, an organism never observed before, resembling a Pyrossomatid, appeared twice. On sedimentary bottoms, which often exhibited sand ripples, scattered fauna such as the actiniid *Bolocera tuediae* and the goniasterid *Peltaster placenta* were observed—these are typically sparse, or solitary organisms present at low densities. The ichthyofauna recorded consisted of *Neocyttus helgae*, several Anguilliformes (including *Synaphobranchus kaupii* and *Halosaurus macrochir*), and one small shark, *Etmopterus* sp.

We finished our day at around 17:30 and decided not to carry out any further dives in this area, as the day was coming to an end. Leaving for Mar da Prata at that time would give us the possibility to work there for a full day.

Figure 7. Location of Pico Sul and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 17th of August 2025.

Figure 8. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Pico Sul, 17th June 2025.

18 August 2025

Even though our arrival at Mar da Prata Sul was scheduled for 11:00, the team got up at the usual time to organize the day ahead. Given the high probability of encountering lost fishing lines in this area, we decided to prepare the “original” Azor Drift-Cam (without the latest improvements) and to deploy the 1200 m umbilical cable, preserving the only 1500 m cable available for the rest of the mission. We conducted a total of 3 dives (St004-006) between 313 and 989 m depth. We reached Mar da Prata at around 11:15 and, after assessing the drift, relocated slightly to the east side of the bank, where the prevailing N/NE current allowed deployment.

The first dive, carried out under calm sea conditions, was successful, with a stable southwest drift that ascended through deeper sectors of the southern margin of the bank. The second dive also proceeded smoothly, with favourable drift and only occasional assistance from the captain to reach the desired area. The third dive, planned for a shallower sector, began with good drift and stable navigation but was interrupted when the system became entangled in fishing line. The equipment was recovered without major damage, apart from the loss of the live view, which the cable was promptly repaired. Although another dive was initially planned, operations were interrupted when the captain reported the need for a hull inspection in Santa Maria, following

observations of ink release from the vessel. The inspection confirmed no structural damage, and the mission continued toward the Heitor Álvares seamount, scheduled for arrival early the next morning.

At the deeper areas explored, the bottom was characterized by soft sediments where sparse fauna (e.g. *Acanella arbuscula*, *Aristaeopsis edwardsiana*) showed up, overall showing poor diversity. When the substrate progressively changed to be more consolidated, a higher diversity of corals and sponges appears. The cnidarians assemblages in deeper areas were composed of *Muriceides paucituberculata*, *Errina atlantica*, *Pleurocorallium jonhsonni*, *Placogorgia* cf. *intermedia* and dense patches of *Candidella imbricata* while the poriferan assemblages observed were formed by *Geodia pachidermata*, *Petrosia clavata* and large aggregations of *Pheronema carpenteri*, sometimes in clumps together with the whip primnoid *Narella versluysi*. When decreasing in depth, the prevalence of hard substrate with large boulders and continuous rock marked a transition to a different sponge assemblage. Here, we observed *Leiodermatium pffeifferae*, *Characella pachastrelloides*, *Characella* sp., *Macandrewia azorica*, *Desmacella grimaldii*, the repent form of the petrosiid *Xestospongia variabilis* and many undetermined encrusting sponges. Cnidarians were not abundant at this area. However, some large specimens of *Callogorgia verticillata*, small plexaurids cf. *Placogorgia terceira* and a few individuals of *Errina atlantica*, *Acanthogorgia* spp. and soft corals cf. *Aquaumbra* sp. were depicted. The mobile fauna was also scarce, with few fishes recorded, such as *Cyttopsis rosea*, juveniles of the bluemouth rockfish *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, some anguiliformes, *Chaunax pictus*, and the decapod *Bathynectes maravigna*. The last dive was suddenly interrupted by fishing cables cutting communication with the live view. However, both cameras were continuously recording the rock, in very interesting “close ups”, showing the high diversity of encrusting demosponges at these areas.

Figure 9. Location of Mar da Prata S and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 18th of August 2025.

Figure 10. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Mar da Prata S, 18th June 2025.

19 August 2025

We began the day with slightly stronger winds as we arrived at our working site, the Heitor Álvares seamount. We returned to the standard configuration currently in use, deploying the improved Drift-Cam with the 1500 m umbilical cable. A total of 5 dives (St007-011) were performed between 586 and 1148 m depth.

With a natural drift toward the southeast, we started on the NW flank of the seamount. The objective of the first dive was to cover the widest depth range possible. The drift was stable at the beginning but deteriorated toward the end of the dive. Unfortunately, the USBL system had a critical configuration missing, and it could not be used during this deployment. The second dive was directed to a shallower area, targeting rocky bottoms. Drift conditions were favourable, and we reached the summit of a small mount. Upon recovery, we noted that the external power supply for the GoPro camera had failed due to low battery voltage. The battery was replaced, and one concentric light was also substituted due to LED displacement. The drift during the first two dives was generally stable, with only minor adjustments required from the captain. In the third dive, however, the drift changed near the shallower section of the seamount, carrying the Drift-Cam around its flank. For the fourth dive, we attempted to take advantage of this drift pattern and adjusted the starting point accordingly. Yet, even before deployment, it became evident that the drift was no longer toward the NE as expected but had shifted to SE. After repositioning the vessel to account for this, the drift shifted once more to the north. For the final dive of the day, we chose a deeper sector where the drift conditions allowed less room for error, aiming to compensate for the variability experienced earlier.

The deeper sector explored today had a substrate that was mostly sedimentary, with a high accumulation of sand forming ripples and sometimes with extended coral rubble deposit areas with slabs of calcareous crusts. These areas were generally poor in terms of fauna, with exceptional and sparse occurrences of *Acanella arbuscula* and *Pliobothrus symmetricus* attached to the occasional cobbles. When the substrate type changed to a sedimentary flat rock, the community composition was characterized by sparse *Leiopathes glaberrima* and by *Chrysogorgia agassizi*, *Acanella arbuscula* in larger densities. Although in lower abundances, other species such as *Vaughanella concinna*, *Paramuricea* sp., *Bathypathes* sp. and *Iridogorgia* sp. were observed too. The

poriferans were also sparse, but many interesting species, such as *Polymastia corticata*, *Oopsacas minuta* and *Chonelasma* sp., were found at the hard substrate.

At upper areas, substrate is totally hard bottom (mainly cemented carbonated calcareous rock) colonised by the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima* in very high densities. Several other cnidarian species were found, for instance the antipatharian *Parantipathes hironnelle*, small plexaurids *Acanthogorgia* spp., the soft coral Aquauridae and hydroids Plumariidae. Sponges were also frequent at this community, with a few records of Haplosclerids, the tubular *Haliclona magna*, the globular *Petrosia clavata*, small specimens of cf. *Phakellia ventilabrum* and the lamellate *Desmacella grimaldii*. Although, the poor invertebrate's diversity, we were able to record the elasmobranchs *Dipturus oxyrinchus* and the *Etmopterus* cf. *pusillus*, and the fishes macrourid *Nezumia aequalis* and several Anguilliformes, such as Nettastomatidae and *Synaphobranchus kaupii*.

Dives were concluded at approximately 20:00.

Figure 11. Location of Heitor Álvares and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 19th of August 2025.

Figure 12. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Heitor Álvares, 19th June 2025.

20 August 2025

We began our day with the objective of completing the Heitor Álvares area, moving approximately 12 nm southwest to carry out dives on a secondary mount. Conditions were favourable, with relatively calm sea and wind, although such circumstances often make drift control more challenging. We carried out a total of 2 dives (St012-013) in this area, between 674 and 776 m depth.

Given the difficulties experienced with the USBL system the previous day, we requested that the captain switch off the ship's probe to determine whether it was interfering with the quality of the acoustic signal. During the first dive, the drift was stable toward the northeast, leading into one of the shallower sections of the mount (~500 m depth). Near the end of the dive, however, the system became entangled in a lost fishing line. After more than an hour of joint effort by all teams, the drift-cam was successfully released and retrieved with no visible structural damage, though the umbilical cable required multiple repairs. The second dive proceeded smoothly and calmly, with at least two depth strata fully explored. This smaller mount within the Heitor Álvares area showed clear evidence of fishing activity, with numerous lost lines and other traces of strong exploitation. Following these dives, we transited for two hours toward the next work area, Alcatraz. Upon arrival, one additional dive (St014) was completed, between 712 and 969 m depth, under very favourable drift conditions. Toward the end of the dive, the system encountered a large basaltic wall where lost fishing lines were again evident. When recovered, the system carried attached to it a hook typically used for wreckfish, along with several fishing lines and a weight.

Lower slopes explored were mainly constituted for sedimentary rock intersected with deposits of coral rubble and detrital bottoms. Megafaunal assemblage was generally poor in abundance and richness, nevertheless composed by sparse sessile organisms. The cnidarians showed a scattered presence of *Acanella arbuscula*, *Chrysogorgia agassizi* and *Errina atlantica*. When the rock outcrops, it revealed the occurrence of a few black corals *Leiopathes expansa*, solitary *Parantipathes hirondelle* and plexaurids *Muriceides paucituberculata*. The sponges were very scarce, but we were able to identify some exemplars of *Characella* sp., *Petrosia clavata* and *Exsuperantia archipelagus*.

At the upper sectors, the hard substrate host interesting sponge's assemblage: encrusting demosponges (e.g. *Hexadella* sp., *Hymedesmia paupertas*, *Phlyctaenopora bitorquis*, and many others, encrusting "white", "yellow" and "orange" Indeterminate) are the most abundant and diverse species. Some massive specimens of *Characella pachastrelloides* complex and other astrophorids cf. *Stryphnus* sp. were found, and it was possible to observe that one of them was allowing a sheltered place for a fish. Digitate and globular sponges, such as *Exsuperantia archipelagus*, *Petrosia vansoesti*, *Haliclona filholi* were also observed. The only cnidarian noticed at this dive was the black coral *Parantipathes hirondelle*. The mobile fauna was also deprived of abundance, merely represented by a kitefin shark *Dalatias licha*, decapods *Chaceon affinis*, echinoderms Goniasteridae and cf. *Peltaster* sp., and a few macrourids fishes, anguiliformes *Synapobranchus kaupi* and a fish school formed by *Hoplosthetus mediterraneus* at the very beginning of the first dive.

The day's work concluded at around 19:00, after which the team held a barbecue on board.

Figure 13. Location of Heitor Álvares and Alcatraz and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 20th of August 2025.

Figure 14. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Heitor Álvares and Alcatraz, on 20th August 2025.

21 August 2025

The weather worsened slightly, though not enough to interrupt operations. Our objective for the day was to conduct additional deployments in the Alcatraz area, focusing this time on the deeper sectors. A total of 3 dives (St015–St017) were performed, between 444 and 1076 m depth.

The first dive followed a very stable and regular drift, consistently toward the NW and N. For these deeper operations, two depth/temperature sensors were attached to the drift-cam, as the Aquatech Aqualogger has a maximum depth rating of 1185 m. During the first two dives, the USBL system functioned intermittently down to 1000 m, without a constant response. In the final, shallower dive, the system worked throughout the deployment and showed an expected drift. The second dive also followed a northern drift, allowing exploration of some deep peaks on the eastern side of the Alcatraz complex. For the third dive, we shifted to shallower areas, as manoeuvring the vessel had become increasingly difficult with the strengthening wind. The drift was

good overall, but the dive was terminated early after encountering several lost fishing lines and approaching a zone between two small peaks where such gear is frequently found.

In the deepest parts of Alcatraz area, the substrate type indicated high sedimentation and concretion of carbonates establishing crusts of sedimentary rock. Substrate composition is complex, with rock outcrops formed by basalt and lava flows, but also by sedimentary rock cementing between basalts. Sedimentary accumulation layers formed by coral rubble, bio detrital sandy bottom are covering large areas too. These sectors presented an exuberant diversity of corals and sponges. Large *Leiopathes expansa*, *Paramuricea* sp., *Acanella arbuscula*, *Chrysogorgia agassazi*, *Madrepora oculata*, *Lophelia pertusa*, *Errina atlantica*, *Candidella imbricata*, *Pliobothrus symmetricus*, *Vaughanella concinna* are some of the cnidarians attached to large rock outcrops (varying from pillow lavas to sedimentary rock). The sponge community is also quite interesting and diverse, with many hexactinellids such as *Hertwigia falcifera*, *Asconema* cf. *setubalense*, *Chonelasma* sp., *Farrea occa* and cf. *Hexactinella grimaldii*. Lamellate demosponges such as *Phakellia ventilabrum*, *Poecillastra compressa* and *Desmacella grimaldii* were frequent. Large white massive demosponges cf. *Stryphnus ponderosus* were recorded too. Notwithstanding, other invertebrates *Cidaris cidaris*, Goniasteridae sp., purple crinoids, and *Bathylasma* sp. are quite abundant along the transect. When getting closer to the upper slope and summit, vertical walls started to appear with several cnidarian species attached (such as plexaurids *Muriceides* sp., *Placogorgia terceira*, *Errina atlantica*).

Arriving to the mount top, a large aggregation of *Viminella flagellum* shows up. This community has several specimens of large, massive barrels or thick lamellate forms of *Characella pachastrelloides* complex, *Nethea amygdaloides*, massive irregular forms of *Petrosia crassa* and the globular *Geodia* sp. It was also perceived many fishing lines all over the *V. flagellum* fields, crossing through the massive sponges, indicating anthropogenic disturbance. Fishes such as Nettastomatidae species, *Neocyttus helgae*, *Synapobranchus kaupii* and macrourids *Nezumia aequalis* and *Coryphaenoides* were the most common species, along with a especial sighting of the elasmobranch *Chimarea* sp.

At the end of the day, we began our transit to Praia da Vitória, on Terceira Island, where we planned to remain the following day due to an adverse weather forecast.

Figure 15. Location of Alcatraz and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 21st of August 2025.

Figure 16. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Alcatraz, on 21st August 2025.

22 August 2025

On this day we remained on land due to adverse weather, mainly the moderate to strong winds affecting the east side of Terceira Island. The vessel was harboured in Praia da Vitória. Some team members used the morning to rest, walk, or exercise, while in the afternoon we focused on data organization, equipment repairs, and maintenance of the Azor Drift-Cam. Two concentric lights were repaired, along with one light lid with dual connectors, a GoPro housing lid glass, and both projectors of the Drift-Cam, which had presented failures during the previous day's final dive. After discussion with the crew and captain, it was decided that the vessel would depart at dawn toward Dom João de Castro seamount, where operations were planned for the following day.

23 August 2025

The RV Arquipélago left the harbour of Praia da Vitória at around 04:00 in the morning, heading toward Dom João de Castro seamount. The conditions for the day were positive with only a light breeze and small swell although a severe storm was forecast within two days. It was therefore decided that this would be the final day of operations before returning to Horta. During the day we performed a total of 6 dives (St018-023), between 245 and 1029 m depth.

The first dive proceeded with an excellent drift, straight and consistent, covering several depth sectors. The second and fifth dives, however, were less successful due to poor drift, which prevented us from reaching the

target areas. The remaining dives achieved stable navigation and satisfactory coverage. Prior to the final dive of the day, the live-view system suddenly stopped functioning without apparent cause. The team promptly tested everything and put it working again, though this incident created some stress given the tight schedule. Consequently, the dive was shorter than expected, and because of the shallow depth and the possibility of entanglement in fishing lines at the top of the ridge, the dive was concluded earlier than planned.

The deepest areas explored were characterized by diverse substrate that range from extensive sedimentary areas to hard substrate, varying between pebbles and boulders to large rock outcrops (St018), and even by lava flows, with typical “pillow lavas”, showing a more recent substrate (St019). Both dives had low abundance and biodiversity but we were still able to record several benthic species, among them the black corals *Antipathes dichotoma*, *Leiopathes expansa* and *Stichopathes gravieri*; the stony corals *Lophelia pertusa* (both alive and dead), *Madrepora oculata* and *Leptopsammia formosa*; the hydrozoans *Pliobothrus symmetricus* and *Errina atlantica*; several gorgonians species like *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, *Candidella imbricata*, *Chrysogorgia agassizi* and specimens of the genus *Muriceides*; and soft corals from the genus *Aquaumbra* and a undetermined soft coral resembling an *Alcyonum* sp. The hexactinellids sponges *Farrea occa* and *Regadrella phoenix* were the most frequent species, but we were lucky to record a large specimen of the genus *Chonelasma*. The mobile fauna observed was several *Mora moro*, isolated *Trachyscorpia cristulata*, macrourids and anguiliformes.

At intermediate depth we noticed a shift in species composition and the cnidarians observed were small specimens of *Callogorgia verticillata*, *Aquaumbra* sp., *Pseudoanthomasthus* sp. and Plumariidae. Sponges' composition was formed by small digitate *Exsuperantia archipelagus*, and the semi-globular forms of *Petrosia* sp. and *Haliclona filholi*, but also a few massive species such as *Leiodermatium pffeiferae*, *Geodia* sp., *Characella pachastrelloides* and *Nethea amygdaloides*. The mobile fauna was formed by sparse sea stars of the Goniasteridae family, the sea urchins *Cidaris cidaris* and a few bluemouth rockfish *Helicolenus dactylopterus* and *Trachyscorpia cristulata*. During the 4th dive of the day, the drift was so bad that we decided to cancel the dive, but while drifting in the mainly sandy bottom we noticed the presence of *Flabellum chunni* laying at the sand.

The substrate found in the shallower areas of this seamount was hard and formed by rocky outcrops that hosted a higher abundance and/or density of the gorgonians *Callogorgia verticillata* and both white and yellow morphotypes of the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*. Other species commonly found were the gorgonians *Paracalyptrophora josephinae*, *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor*, *Acanthogorgia* spp., cf. *Placogorgia terceira* and the soft coral *Pseudoanthomasthus* sp. Surprisingly, we found tiny *Narella* cf. *bellissima*, uncommon at these depths, as well as small plexaurids cf. *Bebryce molis*. Sponge fauna was formed by *Leiodermatium pffeiferae* (blue and white morphs), *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Haliclona (Soestella) implexa*, *Petrosia crassa*, *Petrosia vansoesti*, *Macandrewia azorica* and indeterminate encrusting demosponges. Along all transect it appears what might be a dead seaweed (brown and still fresh) that is laying at the bottom, possibly being washed out from the seamount top where photosynthesis occurs. Fish schools of *Anthias anthias* and *Calanthias ruber* were very common, occasional *Hoplostethus mediterraneus*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Pontinus kuhli* and *Aulopus filamentosus* were spotted. One elasmobranch, *Galeorhinus galeus* was detected too. It is important to refer that we found a lot of lost longlines in this area, possible indicating a high fishing impact pressure at the D. João de Castro.

Following this final deployment, the vessel began its return to Horta, arriving at approximately 05:00 the following morning, one day earlier than initially scheduled due to the approaching storm.

Figure 17. Location of Dom João de Castro and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 23rd of August 2025.

Figure 18. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Dom João de Castro, on 23rd August 2025.

3 MAPGES 2025 RV ARQUIPÉLAGO: EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES: LEG 2 – SEAMOUNTS ON THE MID-ATLANTIC RIDGE.

3.1 SUMMARY OF THE LEG2 OF MAPGES 2025 ARQUIPÉLAGO CRUISE

Objective: to conduct a rapid appraisal of the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and adjacent areas, on board of the research vessel Arquipélago. These dives aim to contribute to the overall goal of better understanding the composition and diversity of deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species and assess their environmental status.

Statistics: We performed 32 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1230 m depth, covering 27 km of the seafloor and producing 49 hours of video footage, 2.3 TB of disc space.

Vessel: RV Arquipélago

Dates: 28 August - 04 September 2025

Scientific team: Luís Rodrigues (Chief scientist), Gabriela Cardoso, Guilherme Gonçalves and Inês Bruno

Figure 19. Scientific team of RV Arquipélago that participated in the Leg 2 of MapGES 2025 cruise.

3.2 HIGHLIGHTS

- 1- During Leg 2 of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, we were able to perform **32 valid dives** with the Azor drift-cam, covering a wide range of depth strata (**633 - 1235 m depth**). We explored about **27 km** of the seafloor and produced **49:11** hours of video footage, adding up to about **2.3 TB** of storage space.
- 2- **We were able to successfully visit and sample 5 new geomorphological units for the first time:** Beta W, Buchanan N, A10, A13 and Alfa Profundo. The other areas that had been already visited (most of which during MapGES 2019 cruise) either lacked in depth range representativeness (Beta, Ferradura E, Picoto, Alfa and Alfa E), and/or regarding overall area covered (Beta, Picoto), which meant a more thorough data collection was needed. With the Azor drift-cam's recent improvements in lightning, video durability, and operational depth range, we revisited these sites to obtain higher-quality data.

- 3- We explored **depths greater than 1200 m** - a first for the Azor drift-cam - which, once more, proves the **camera system's effectiveness and capabilities** in covering large bathymetric gradients, with all its components successfully handling the high pressures of the most demanding environments.
- 4- During the iMAR 2022 cruise we managed to perform a multibeam survey that covered an area which revealed to be much shallower and characterized by more features than previous maps showed: Beta W. The multibeam survey revealed a 4 km-long summit shallower than 800 m, which added, at the time, a new area to our list of exploration targets. Similarly to Diogo de Teive and Estrela seamounts, this newly mapped area could potentially represent a **pristine and reference unit that could play an important role in quantifying the real impacts** of bottom-longline fishing on the deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, as it sits in the bottom-longline fishing range depths. However, the **benthic communities found here were somewhat poor**, in the shallowest sector explored, which raises more questions regarding this topic and **urgency in surveying and assessing human-induced impacts** on benthic habitats in the Azores.
- 5- During the exploration of Ferradura E area, the deeper sectors revealed **unique and localized megabenthic communities** usually composed of a large variety of species. We recorded what we think could be **one of the densest aggregations of the large yellow hexactinellid *Hertwigia falcifera***. This species was very sporadically recorded before this leg, which raises the question of which specific environmental factors might be triggering this localized hotspot for this sponge. The surrounding benthic community was also surprisingly rich, considering the elevated fishing effort practice in this seamount. The **deeper communities appear to be sheltered and out of reach of the human activities** that mostly occur in more intermediate depths, where **visible clear impacts can be observed on large *Callogorgia verticillata***.
- 6- Also, in Ferradura E seamount, our cameras documented a **vast and dense aggregation of the primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*** at around 850 m depth, extending along almost an entire ridge. While *Narella*-dominated communities are common across many Azorean seamounts, the diversity recorded along this ridge surpassed that observed at most comparable depths. In addition to the dominant primnoids, a wide array of other taxa was present. Particularly noteworthy was the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*, **represented by medium-sized colonies** occurring frequently throughout the ridge and often serving as **host for the decapod *Sternostylus formosus***.
- 7- While exploring the previously codenamed area A10, our camera system was unexpectedly visited by a very pale, ghostly-looking ray—possibly representing the **first record of the Mid-Atlantic skate *Rajella cf. kukujevi*** in the Azores. Its mysterious appearance, the calm way it approached, and the time it lingered in front of the camera, were particularly striking. On the live-view feed, its blurry outline but strikingly white coloration reminded us of a ghost. Inspired by this encounter, the **A10 area was subsequently renamed “Fantas” seamount**, a short form of *Fantasma* (“ghost” in Portuguese), after this alien-like creature.
- 8- The **Menez Gwen area** is one the most enigmatic seamounts of the Azorean EEZ. Its two hydrothermal vents, discovered in 1994 set the stage for various expeditions that took place there ever since. However, the Azor drift-cam was never deployed there, and, despite having performed one dive during the iMAR 2022 cruise on its eastern ridge, most of this remarkable geomorphological structure was still to be explored representatively in all its magnitude. We could not have picked a better spot to perform the **longest dive to date with the Azor drift-cam**. To start with, the substrate on particular sectors was impressive, with apparently **geologically recent pillows** with very little to no sediment deposition,

dominating vast sectors of the explored seabed. In addition to this, scattered along these recent hardgrounds were impressive **large-sized colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* and of the genus *Placogorgia***, with occasional lace corals *Lophellia pertusa* also composing this interesting benthic community.

- 9- The deep, wide and long ridge that extends for 15 nm in a south-to-north orientation in **Picoto seamount revealed rich megabenthic communities**. One of the surveyed sectors revealed a surprisingly diverse megabenthic assemblage, contrasting with the rather modest impression we had while navigating the system in real time. An **extensive aggregation of the corals *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia* sp. was observed, likely among the largest and densest yet recorded in the Azores**. This community also supported a vast array of associated taxa, such as the stylasterid *Errina atlantica*, the gorgonians *Candidella imbricata*, *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor*, multi-coloured plexaurids, abundant fan-shaped sponges *Phakellia ventilabrum*, and several other hexactinellids. Basalts sheltered **noteworthy colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa***, as well as massive plate-shaped white demosponges, one observed serving as **substrate for the king crab *Chaceon affinis***, together with the framework-building scleractinians *Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa*. Additionally, the presence of *Iridogorgia* sp. and the yellow glass sponge *Hertwigia falcifera*, though more sporadic, was higher than typically recorded in similar habitats.
- 10- At Alfa seamount, three dives documented particularly remarkable communities, especially on the shallowest and intermediate slopes surveyed. These sectors hosted a **“forest” of massive *Paragorgia johnsoni* (bubble-gum coral) colonies**, exhibiting both morphotypes, but mostly white. These are certainly among the **largest examples of this species observed with our camera system to date**. Associated with this aggregation were dense patches of soft corals *Pseudoanthomastus* sp., large demosponges identified as *Characella connectens*, and strikingly high numbers of the echinoid *Cidaris cidaris*, colonizing the steep substrate.

Figure 20. Location of the 32 video transects (yellow lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 2 of MapGES 2025 on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Figure 21. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 2 of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago showing examples of megabenthic fauna and communities recorded during the cruise: **(a)** Large hexactinellid sponge *Hertwigia falcifera*; **(b)** Extensive primnoid aggregation of *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*; **(c)** Two large colonies of *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor* in excellent condition; **(d)** Slopes colonized by the bubble-gum coral *Paragorgia johnsoni*; **(e)** Impressive colony of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* attached to an outcrop, hosting the decapod *Sternostylus formosus*; **(f)** A delicate, solitary *Iridogorgia* sp. on a barren seabed; **(g)** Large colonies of *Placogorgia* sp. colonizing fresh pillow lavas; **(h)** Basalt overhangs sheltering *Leiopathes expansa* and large plate-shaped demosponges; **(i)** Massive hexactinellid sponge *Chonelasma* sp.; **(j)** A pale, long-lived orange roughly *Hoplostethus atlanticus* roaming a deep summit; **(k)** Portuguese dogfish *Centroscymnus coelolepis*, first recorded with the Azor drift-cam; **(l)** Potential first record in the Azores of the Mid-Atlantic skate *Rajella* cf. *kukujevi*.

3.3 CRUISE DIARY OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO LEG 2

25-27 August 2025

After the RV Arquipélago was refuelled and re-stocked from the previous leg, we were prepared to depart Horta harbour with a newly restructured scientific team. However, the start of the Leg had to be postponed twice. The first delay was due to an unfavourable weather forecast resulting from the passage of storm Erin north of the archipelago, on the 25th. The second occurred on the afternoon of the 26th, just before our planned departure, when we received news that a pipe in the engine's cooling system required repair.

The issue got fixed by the evening of the 27th and we were finally ready to start the Leg 2.

28 August 2025

The original plan for Leg 2 focused on surveying unexplored seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic ridge, while also complementing the exploration previously performed in others. As such, we left Horta harbour towards Ferradura E area, located 75 nm southwest of Faial Island, at around 23:30 of the previous day, to arrive in time for the first dive of the Leg, at around 08:20. During the MapGES 2019 cruise, also aboard the RV Arquipélago, the Azor Drift-Cam completed its first series of dives in this area, with eight deployments conducted between 400 and 850 m. However, we lacked the exploration of intermediate depths and greater than 800 m. Today we managed to explore sectors between 550 m and 1170 m deep, completing 4 successful dives throughout the day (St024-St027).

During the morning dives, the prevalent winds from the Northeast enabled relatively consistent and long drifts, directing the camera system towards the planned endpoints. In contrast, during the afternoon dives, conditions shifted: wind speed decreased and changed direction, while bottom currents exerted stronger influence on the system's trajectory. During these cases, drifts were quite random, unexpected and slow, which made dive-planning decisions much harder to make. There were no major technical issues during the day. However, after the last dive we noticed that the cable that feeds the GoPro externally was broken, and the camera was disconnected. It is possible that the camera did not record the entire dive, but we could not retrieve the videos due to a card error.

The deeper strata of the day were colonized by a remarkably diverse megabenthic community, where the rocky basalts held very high biodiversity of corals and sponges. The Cnidaria group was represented by several species: the primnoid *Candidella imbricata*, the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula*, the gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe*, *H. tricolor* and *Chrysogorgia* sp., multi-coloured colonies belonging to the family Plexauridae, lots of reef-building scleractinians such as *Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa* and black coral colonies of the species *Leiopathes expansa*, *Parantipathes hirondelle* and *Schyzopathidae* sp. The Porifera group was equally impressive, but what caught us by surprise the most was the size and density of the hexactinellids *Hertiwigia falcifera*, which, up until this specific dive was very sparsely recorded by the Azor drift-cam. It is strikingly impressive to realize that after more than 1000 dives with the Azor drift-cam we still record pleasantly unexpected surprises like these.

The intermediate depths explored revealed interesting faunal assemblages usually dominated by the primnoid corals *Narella* spp. and large colonies of *Callogorgia verticillata*. The former appeared in the usual astonishingly dense aggregations, covering large sectors of one particular ridge, while the latter was mostly characterized by a poor conservation status, displaying high levels of impacts potentially triggered by human activities in the area. Within this community, many *Pseudoanthomasthus* sp., small gorgonians *Acanthogorgia* spp. and *Paragorgia johnsoni*, impressively large corals likely of the Paramuriceidae family, several medium-sized colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* as well as *Parantipathes hirondelle*, were recorded as well. Large demosponges such as *Petrosia crassa* and *Xestospongia friabilis* and hexactinellids that included *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Farrea occa*, *Asconema fristedti* and *Regadrella phoenix* were also frequently recorded. Kite fin sharks *Dalatias licha*, the monkfish *Lophius piscatoris*, the bluemouth rockfish *Helicolenus dactylopterus* were observed near these depths as well. Motile fauna at these depths included several *Neocyttus helgae*, mora fish *Mora moro* and lots of eel-like fishes roaming close to the seabed.

We ended the last dive at around 19:20 and started to head towards Beta seamount, which we would sample the next day.

Figure 22. Location of Ferradura E area and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 28th of August 2025.

Figure 23. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 28th August of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Ferradura E area.

29 August 2025

After drifting overnight near Beta seamount, we assessed the prevalent drift direction and repositioned the vessel at the desired starting point for the first transect of the day, which began at approximately 08:20. We initiated by exploring the deeper and southern-most areas of the seamount, which hadn't been explored previously during the MapGES 2019 campaign. While the shallowest areas had been visited in that year, no depth or temperature data were collected during those dives, providing an additional reason to conduct a more

comprehensive survey. Bathymetric data for Beta remain of relatively poor quality, so we were aware that our planned transects might not align perfectly with the actual geomorphological features. Nevertheless, we performed 4 successful dives (St028-St031) across a depth gradient of 633 and 1168 m depth.

Drift conditions proved challenging, particularly during the morning dives. Based on the prevailing south-westerly winds, we expected the vessel to drift eastward, yet the transects were instead directed predominantly southward. The captain had to constantly adjust the vessel position in relation to the umbilical, which frequently passed beneath the hull. During the afternoon the wind speed increased substantially and with it, the speed of the vessel during the transects. It was not easy to navigate the camera system close to the seabed, as the constant tension on the umbilical meant it was very easily lifted off the bottom. During the recovery of the last dive of the day, the tension on the umbilical was such that the electric cable broke near the winch. Despite these operation difficulties, we still recorded interesting fauna.

While exploring the deeper strata of Beta, the seabed was characterized by intermittent flat basalts within a sandy-dominated terrain, which held little benthic fauna. However, the hard grounds were usually colonized by the gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor*, some of which appeared in relatively large sizes and in some spots in relatively high densities. Some of the colonies, however, appeared dead and upturned on the seabed. The whip coral *N. versluysi* also appeared at this depth strata in very high abundances at times, usually colonizing flat grounds. The fan-shaped sponge *Phakellia ventilabrum* was also observed. Other cnidarians included the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula*, its gorgonian look-alike *Chrysogorgia* sp. and colonies belonging to the family Paramuriceidae, all of which appeared more sporadically. *Deania* sp. sharks were observed, as well as a couple squids *Mastogothia* sp.

The shallowest and more intermediate depths explored held similar communities to those found on Ferradura E seamount on the previous day: *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima* characterized most of the assemblages found along the slopes at these depths, despite not as dense as the aggregation found on Ferradura E. Similarly, several other species were found along this community: occasional colonies of *Callogorgia verticillata*, black corals *Leiopathes expansa* and *Parantipathes* sp., stylasterids *Errina atlantica*, soft corals *Pseudoantomasthus* sp. the vase-shaped sponge *Asconema fristedti*, the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*, many demosponges including *Petrosia crassa* and *Characella pachastrelloides* and several lamellate sponges growing on the edges of the basalts encountered. During the last dive, we came across one of the transects made in 2019, during which we had encountered large *Paragorgia johnsoni* colonies. Indeed, today we drifted over many colonies of the same species of both red and white morphs, as well as lots of concomitant taxa along the same slope. These included dense patches of *Narella versluysi*, soft corals, a small orange pleaxurid coral, solitary stony corals *Leptopsammia formosa*, and many large demosponges: *Petrosia crassa*, *Xestospongia friabilis*, *Desmacella grimaldii* and *Poecillastra compressa*. We also drifted over some fishes such as *Mora moro*, *Trachyscorpia cristulata*, the silver-roughy *Hoplostethus mediterraneus*, the monkfish *Lophius piscatorius*, the shrimp *Aristeopsis edwardsiana* and some echinoids *Cidaris cidaris*.

We ended the last dive of the day at around 19:35 and began the short transit towards Beta W seamount.

Figure 24. Location of Beta seamount and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 29th of August 2025.

Figure 25. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 29th August of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Beta seamount.

30 August 2025

After checking the direction of drift, we positioned the vessel to start exploring the Beta W seamount, a structure whose features were for the most part deeper than 700 m. We collected high quality bathymetry during the iMAR 2022 cruise, which revealed the geomorphological characteristics of the structure in great detail. We started exploring the northern-most ridges of the area, at around 08:30, expecting southwards drifts.

We conducted 4 successful dives during the day (St032-035), mostly on deep grounds, between 800 m and 1232 m deep, breaking the record for the deepest dive conducted with the Azor drift-cam (validated with depth sensor data). Morning drifts were strong and steady, directing the system reliably toward the planned endpoints. By contrast, wind speeds decreased in the afternoon, resulting in much slower transects.

A significant portion of the day was dedicated to troubleshooting an issue with the 1500 m umbilical cable, which appeared to have lost connection partway along its length. During the recovery of the first dive, we lost the live view image near to the surface. After reaching the vessel we started testing the components of the live view system and concluded that there was no signal from the electrical cable. Although this cable had been heavily damaged during the previous leg and subsequently repaired, all connections remained intact, and no new external damage was visible. The problem seemed localized to a specific section of the cable that failed to transmit signal even after both ends were reconnected. This was puzzling to the team, but with the support of the RV Arquipélago crew, and the unexpected use of a light bulb as a diagnostic tool, we confirmed that the cable was, in fact, still transmitting.

We began by exploring the deeper sectors of Beta W, which held outcropping basalts mixed with consolidated sediments. The usual megabenthic assemblages found here were mostly dominated by the gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe* and *Hemicorallium tricolor* in higher abundances than those we usually see, but other species occurred as well, despite more sporadically. The reef-building *Madrepora oculata*, several colonies of plexaurids in varying colors, the gorgonian *Candidella imbricata*, the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* and one small colony of *Iridogorgia* sp., not commonly recorded with the Azor drift-cam. In regard to the phylum Porifera, some additional species were observed at these depths: the fan-shaped *Phakellia ventilabrum*, lamellate sponges *Desmacella grimaldii* and *Poecillastra compressa*, the bird's nest *Pheronema carpenteri* and one large *Geodia megastrella*. Other smaller hexactinellids were present as well. The sea-urchin *Cidaris cidaris* was also a common occurrence among the coral rubble deposits found on flatter terrain. The only slope whose summit we covered above the 800 m revealed a poorer benthic assemblage. Despite having covered almost the entire length of the slope, the only habitual relevant species to inhabit it was the glass sponges *Pheronema carpenteri* and *Asconema fristedti* and some sea stars *Peltaster placenta*, punctually.

We ended the last dive at around 19:50 and started making the short transit towards Buchanan N area.

Figure 26. Location of Beta W seamount and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 30th of August 2025.

Figure 27. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 30th August of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Beta W area.

31 August 2025

After spending a calm night drifting along the plateau of Buchanan N, we positioned the vessel and began the first dive of the day at around 08:15. Given the fact that most stations were performed at relatively deep sectors (below 850 m) and that the geomorphological area is quite large to cover with enough representativeness, we only managed to conduct a total of 4 dives (St036 – St039). We covered a narrow depth range between 924 m and 1234 m, once again breaking the record for the deepest dive conducted with the Azor drift-cam, twice in just two days. To effectively survey the site, a westward drift was required, as the only pronounced depth gradient in the area faces east and extends for roughly 14 nautical miles. However, the prevailing drift carried the vessel toward the southwest. As a result, the captain had to continuously adjust the vessel's position to pull the equipment westward, directing it toward the east-facing slope.

The lower slopes visited were mostly characterized by fine layers of sandy bottoms covering flat rocky grounds. When the hard substrate was visible it was sometimes colonized by the hydroids *Crypthelia* sp. and the bottle-brush shaped corals *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia* sp. The gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor* were occasional sights as well. Punctual solitary cup-corals from the genus *Javania* were visible as well. We realized the different small-scale geomorphological features along the entire length of the area determined completely different types of substrates and associated fauna. As we covered sectors where the slope was more inclined, the prevalent basalts held faunal assemblages a bit richer than the flatter and deeper terrain,

characterized by a different variety of species: the cnidarians *Iridogorgia* sp., *Candidella imbricata*, *Phanopathes erinaceus*, *Crypthelia* sp., bryozoans, several glass sponges (*Regadrella phoenix*, *Hertwigia falcifera*, *Asconema* sp.) and some unidentified fan-shaped hexactinellids. Lamellate sponges such as *Desmacella grimaldii* and cf. *Poecillastra compressa* were also observed colonizing boulders. One particularly interesting aspect of this part of the slope was the distinct substrate that characterized it, composed of a mixture of volcanic basalts and consolidated sediments. Some denser patches of basaltic boulders were more densely colonized by gorgonian *Candidella imbricata* and some hexactinellids, some particularly large. We drifted along lots of macrourids and eel-like fishes roaming close to the seabed, as well as mora fishes *Mora moro*, and managed to get a rare sight of two orange roughies *Hoplostethus atlanticus*. Echinoids *Cidaris cidaris* were also a common sight at these depths. When visiting the upper slopes and flat plateau of this area harbouring little megabenthic fauna.

Figure 28. Location of Buchanan N seamount and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 31st of August 2025.

Figure 29. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 31st August of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Buchanan N.

1 September 2025

Today, we decided to explore the areas codenamed A10 and A13. They are both very similar in structure, with deep summits rising to around 900 m depth, and are separated by approximately 12 nm. Dive planning was therefore crucial to ensure representative coverage of both areas. We began by exploring the southeastern-most seamount (A10) and moved on to A13 after two dives. Despite having a long transit between seamounts, we managed to conduct 3 dives (St040– St042) across 970 m and 1181 m depth, one being aborted however, which slightly compromised today, and the next few days planned work. Nevertheless, with low wind speeds, the natural drift of the vessel provided sufficient movement to cover the desired transects efficiently. The first dive began at 08:25, with the image of a burning-orange sunrise over a perfectly flat sea still fresh in our minds. The first two dives were performed in the larger A10 area, one of them along the large flat summit at around 950 m and the second on a north-facing slope on the northern-most part of the area.

The first revealed sandy substrates but frequently interrupted by fields of consolidated sediments and small hills composed of basaltic outcrops. This area was relatively poor in terms of benthic biodiversity throughout its entire length. Nevertheless, we could observe some sessile fauna along the 2-hour dive: the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula*, colonies from the family Plexauridae, *Chrysogorgia* sp., small colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*, the sylasterid *Errina atlantica* and the gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe* and *Candidella imbricata*. The Porifera group was also represented in this area: the hexactinellids *Regradella phoenix* and

Phakellia ventilabrum, white lithistids and the lamellate sponge *Desmacella grimaldii*. The sea-urchin *Cidaris cidaris*, was a common occurrence, as well as the decapod *Aristeopsis edwardsianna*, several eel-like fishes and a mora fish *Mora moro*. While exploring the northern slope that starts at 1200 m and comes up to 930 m deep, similar fauna could be observed.

The northern slope visited was almost entirely characterized by very interesting, consolidated sediments colonized by similar faunal assemblages, although the density of *Acanella arbuscula* and plexaurid corals was higher, making them the dominant taxa observed along the depths explored. In addition to the other species also observed in the first dive, we got a good image of an *Iridogorgia* sp. The camera system was also briefly visited by a mysterious, pale-looking ray that swam calmly in front of us. Its ghostly appearance inspired us to propose a name for the A10 area: “Fantas” Seamount, short for *Fantasma* (Portuguese for “ghost”). After further research and consultation with experts, we concluded that this sighting may represent the first record of the Mid-Atlantic skate *Rajella* cf. *kukujevi* in the Azores.

After a 1:30 transit, we deployed the system at the A13 seamount. Upon descent, the live-view feed became unstable, and once on the bottom it was impossible to navigate, as the screen turned blue almost constantly. The team tested every component of the live-view box individually, but without success. The dive was aborted, and troubleshooting was conducted onboard. After extended testing, we concluded (though not with full certainty) that the issue originated from the analog-to-digital converter receiving the camera signal, or from its connection with the HDMI transmitter. Unfortunately, the problem was only apparently resolved by around 19:00, leaving no time for a proper dive.

Given the circumstances, the decision was made to remain in the vicinity overnight to ensure a full survey of A13 the following day.

Figure 30. Location of Fantas and A13 seamounts and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 1st of September 2025.

Figure 31. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 1st September of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Fantas and A13 seamounts.

2 September 2025

We spent the night drifting eastward, ending up approximately 5 nautical miles from the starting point of the first transect of the day in the A13 area. The wind speed increased considerably overnight, making drifts much stronger. Given the fact that the technical issues from the day before only allowed us to perform two dives, we tried to begin the workday a slightly earlier than usual, starting the first dive at around 08:00. After completing this dive, we transited 12 nm eastward to Menez Gwen seamount, where we carried out two dives perpendicular to the western ridge. This complemented previous work conducted during the iMAR 2022 cruise, when the eastern ridge had been explored. Overall, we managed to complete 4 dives (3 valid; St043 – St046) covering depths between 745 m and 1068 m.

The A13 transect revealed habitats very similar to those observed the previous day at Fantas seamount. The occasional basalt outcrops occur in between large fields of consolidated sediments. Fauna wise, assemblages were quite similar too, with the bottle-brush corals *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia* sp. dominating the benthic community present. Occasional gorgonians such as *Hemicorallium niobe*, *H. tricolor*, *Candidella imbricata* and Plexaurid corals sporadically colonized the seafloor too. The fan-shaped sponge *Phakellia ventilabrum* and several white lamellate hexactinellids were present along the transect as well.

During this dive, the wind increased substantially, making us drift too fast to efficiently and comfortably operate the drift-cam (drifting at speeds close to 2 knots). Nevertheless, we managed to conclude the desired transect successfully and began heading towards Menez Gwen area, where we arrived at 11:35 to explore the ridge to the West and the valley that cuts across both. After lunch, the wind speeds increased even more, reaching up to 40 km/h, resulting in both a very fast and direct drift, but also rendering the navigation of the drift-cam quite challenging due to the velocity of the system along the seabed. In fact, we broke the record for the longest Azor drift-cam dive to date in the second transect with 2.6 km in length. The images recorded revealed quite remarkable substrate heterogeneity, with vast sections of pillow-lavas, appearing to be of recent origin, characterized by lots of crevices, overhangs and small hills, which could potentially be determining various small-scale current regimes. However, this geological variability was not followed by a particularly high

biological richness, much to our surprise. It did, however, hold occasional and concentrated patches of higher biodiversity in some short sectors. While navigating along this jagged terrain, we were able to record lush and long-lived colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* attached to the basalt outcrops, close to other species of corals as well: large colonies of the gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor*, orange Plexaurids, occasional habitat-builders *Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa* (close to which we could frequently observe dead coral framework around the basalt pillows), small patches of *Narella versluysi* and many other associated taxa. The fan-shaped sponge *Phakellia ventilabrum*, white lamellates and hexactinellids *Aphrocallistes beatrix* and *Regadrella phoenix* punctually colonized this substrate as well. Lots of decapods *Chaceon affinis* and *Sternostylus formosus* (often holding themselves to *Leiopathes expansa* colonies), mora fishes *Mora moro*, eel-like fishes and deep-sea sharks, two *Deania* sp. and a large Portuguese dogfish *Centroscymnus coelolepis* - first ever record with the Azor drift-cam - constituted the most relevant mobile fauna observed.

During the third dive of the day, the same technical issues encountered the previous day reappeared: the live-view feed became unstable before reaching the bottom. This time, we decided to recover the system while troubleshooting in parallel. Having already tested all components of the live-view box and the drift-cam, only two possible sources of failure remained: the umbilical cable and the vessel's power supply. Using a car battery to power the live-view system temporarily resolved the problem, but similar issues resurfaced once the dive restarted. The dive was aborted, and the system recovered again. Back on deck, we changed the umbilical (as we did the day before) and the problem got apparently solved again. Closer inspection revealed the underlying cause: the connection between the electrical cable and the 4-pin connector to the drift-cam's live-view cylinder was not watertight. As a result, water progressively infiltrated the cable under pressure during repeated dives. We only managed to solve all these issues at around 18:00, which only allowed one more dive to be conducted. At the end of the dive, we carefully amended this portion of the cable, making a brand new, and now surely water-tight, connection.

At the end of the day, we received a weather broadcast update, which informed us of the impossibility to work on Friday, 5th September. This forced us to reconsider our schedule. Before this, we were considering the possibility of staying one more day in Menez Gwen, given how much the dives performed here surprised us. However, with Picoto, Alfa Profundo, Alfa, and Alfa E seamounts still requiring substantial work and only two operational days remaining, it was no longer feasible to stay. We therefore made the difficult but necessary decision to depart for Picoto seamount to continue the campaign the following day.

Figure 32. Location of A13 and Menez Gwen areas and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 2nd of September 2025.

Figure 33. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 2nd September of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in A13 and Menez Gwen area.

3 September 2025

We woke up near Picoto seamount after drifting overnight in its vicinity. Back in 2019, we had surveyed only the shallowest sectors, confined to the northern part of the geomorphological unit. This time, our objective was to complement that earlier work by exploring deeper sectors and distributing dives more evenly across the entire structure to ensure representative coverage. The first dive began at around 08:00, with the hope that

the technical problems of the previous two days would not resurface. After confirming a southbound drift, we began operations on the steep north-facing slope at the northernmost sector of the area and progressively advanced southward over the course of the day, covering the wide ridge that extends for ~15 nm in a north-south orientation. We also conducted one dive at Alfa Profundo seamount at the end of the day. In total, we performed five dives (St047–St051), across depths ranging from 676 to 1190 m.

During the first dive of the day, one of the lights malfunctioned, but we decided to carry on working and solve this issue by the end of the day. In addition to this, we struggled with issues on the live view feed, once again. It only failed during the deployment of the 3rd dive of the day, leaving us questioning if we'd really found the origin of this problem the day before. We aborted the dive, recovered the equipment quickly, switched the umbilical, and resumed the dive. The problem, most likely, still persists in the 1500m-long cable we have been using.

The lower slopes of Picoto were by far the richest we have encountered so far, not only on the seamount, but likely during this Leg and cruise. The seabed was either characterized by flatter grounds, of consolidated sedimentary origin, either by volcanic basalts, forming vertical walls, overhangs, outcrops and a vast diversity of small-scale features. This variety in geomorphology apparently triggers high levels of associated biodiversity, particularly throughout the long southern ridge of Picoto. As usual, while navigating the system over the seabed, our perception of the level of biodiversity of megabenthic fauna and the natural value these sectors held was that it was rather poor. However, upon viewing the high-quality videos recorded, we were awestruck. Two of the most conspicuous corals at these depths are the bamboo-coral *Acanella arbuscula* and the much-alike gorgonian *Chrysogorgia* sp. and yet, we still managed to record one of the largest and densest aggregations of these usually concomitant species across the Azores. Within this community, lots of other associated taxa: the stylasterid *Errina atlantica*, the gorgonian *Candidella imbricata*, *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor*, plexaurid corals of multiple colours, many fan-shaped sponges *Phakellia ventilabrum*, and several species of hexactinellids. In addition to this, the basalt overhangs hid large, impressive colonies of black corals *Leiopathes expansa*, massive white demosponges with a plate morphology (one of which curiously used by a king crab *Chaceon affinis*) and habitat-builders *Madrepora occulata* and *Lophellia pertusa*. More sporadic, but still more prevalent than usual, the gorgonian *Iridogorgia* sp. and the yellow hexactinellid *Hertwigia falcifera* were spotted as well around these sectors. The eel-like fish *Synapobranchus kaupii* was by far the most abundant mobile species, with multiple individuals appearing at once in front of us, but with mora fishes *Mora moro* and the decapod *Aristaeopsis edwardsianna* also being seen moving close to the seabed.

The shallower sectors explored revealed relatively flat plateaus colonized by the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* in occasionally dense patches, interspersed with aggregations of the priminoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima* often accompanied by other smaller taxa which included the soft coral *Pseudoanthomastus* sp. Schools of *Hoplostethus mediterraneus* and *Beryx* spp. were common sights as well within this depth sectors. The intermediate strata explored revealed a higher heterogeneity of substrate, as large basalt outcrops and tall vertical walls characterized most of the steep slopes observed. This determined markedly different benthic assemblages, mostly characterized by small encrusting sponges and demosponges in varying morphologies.

The last dive of the day was performed on the Alfa Profundo seamount, whose top is rather deep, flat and 4 nm wide. Our objective was to explore its summit for as long as we could. Megabenthic diversity was poorer than in Picoto at the same depths, however, we still managed to record interesting abundant patches of the solitary

stony coral *Leptosammia formosa*, with other species such as *Acanella arbuscula*, small *Leiopathes expansa* colonies, large vases-shaped sponges *Asconema fristedti* and *Regadrella phoenix* also composing the faunal assemblage present.

Figure 34. Location of Picoto and Alfa Profundo seamounts and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 3rd of September 2025.

Figure 35. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 3rd September of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Picoto and Alfa Profundo seamounts.

4 September 2025

Today marked the final day of the MapGES 2025 cruise, as the weather forecast received two days earlier forced us to shorten this leg by one day. As a result, we were forced to divide the workday in two separate areas, once more. However, adverse weather conditions seemed to arrive earlier than anticipated, making the operation of the Azor drift-cam increasingly challenging. Our focus was on Alfa and Alfa E seamounts, located ~5 nm apart. Both had been visited during the MapGES 2019 and iMAR 2022 cruises, yet certain sectors and features still required further exploration to ensure more representative coverage. We began at the westernmost sector of Alfa seamount at around 08:10 in the morning, after having witnessed the last sunrise aboard of RV Arquipélago. We managed to conduct 5 successful dives (St052 - St056), covering a depth gradient of 649 m to 1106 m.

In Alfa seamount, the 3 dives conducted revealed impressive communities, in particular colonizing the shallowest sector explored. A “forest” of massive colonies of the bubble-gum coral *Paragorgia johnsoni* displaying both red and white morphologies was recorded along one of the explored slopes. These are, quite possibly, some of the largest colonies of this species we have recorded so far with our camera system. Within this aggregation, dense patches of soft corals *Pseudoanthomastus* sp., large demosponges possibly from the species *Characella connectens*, and, interestingly, very high numbers of the echinoid *Cidaris cidaris* could be seen colonizing steep slopes. As depth increased within this sector, primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima* formed somewhat dense aggregations together with the bird’s nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*.

The deeper sectors in Alfa harboured equally impressive megabenthic communities, for the most part largely dominated by the bottle-brush corals *Acanella arbuscula* and *Chrysogorgia* sp., in occasionally very high densities (similar to the ones found in Picoto), but with other species being present as well in very high numbers, such as the gorgonians *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor*, the stylasterid *Errina atlantica* and many hexactinellids such as *Phakellia ventilabrum*, *Farrea occa* and *Pheronema carpenteri*. In addition to this, massive sponges from the genus *Chonelasma* sp. also caught our eyes. Mora fishes *Mora moro* and *Trachyscorpia crisutulata* were recorded at these depths too.

After lunch, we had to transit towards Alfa E area to perform 2 more dives. However, during the afternoon, the wind increased substantially, making it almost impossible to smoothly operate the drift-cam close to the seabed. Nevertheless, the sectors explored revealed *Narella versluysi*, *N. bellissima* and *Pheronema carpenteri* aggregations, along a consolidated sedimentary slope. We also observed some vase-shaped *Asconema fristedti* within this community.

The last dive of the day was cut short due to live view feed issues, once again. We began returning to Horta harbour at around 18:50, and making the 110 nm transit during the night, the last of the MapGES 2025 ARQ cruise.

Figure 36. Location of Alfa and Alfa E seamounts and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 4th of September 2025.

Figure 37. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 4th September of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Alfa and Alfa E areas.

5 September 2025

We left the RV Arquipélago at around 07:00 with most of the gear organized, ready to bring back to our offices Monday morning. This was the end of the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago.

4 "LIFE" ON BOARD MT PHYSETER DURING MAPGES 2025

4.1 "LIFE" ON BOARD RV ARQUIPÉLAGO DURING LEG 1 OF THE MAPGES 2025 CRUISE

4.2 "LIFE" ON BOARD RV ARQUIPÉLAGO DURING LEG 2 OF THE MAPGES 2025 CRUISE

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